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Tatar-Bashkird in Turkestan Time Press Activity of Enlighteners

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Annotation: *In this article, an attempt was made to cover the activities of the Tatar-Bashkir enlighteners in the contemporary press in Turkestan. The aim of the colonizers of the Russian Empire to establish the press, the cooperation relations of the modern enlighteners with the Tatar-Bashkir developers on the way to the foundation of the national press were highlighted.*

Key words: *Russian Empire, von Kaufman, "Gazette of the Turkestan Region", Ahmad Zaki Walidi, Shahimardon Ibrohimov, "Sadoi Turkistan", Husayn Makayev, "Flag of Labor", "Unity Flag", "Time", "Translator"*

INTRODUCTION.

When our country became an independent state, the need for a reliable, scientifically based and impartially illuminated history of our people appeared. Because, during the colonial period of the former Soviet Union, historical events were covered within the framework of Marxist-Leninist ideology. After the independence of our country, our thousand-year history is being re-examined on the basis of objectivity and science. Especially on the topic of the formation of the national press and its development, a lot of research has been conducted and is being conducted.

It is known that the years 1870-1917 took place in the history of Uzbekistan as a period of colonialism by the Russian Empire. In this period, the reform activity in the social-political, religious-educational life of Turkestan is distinguished by its wide scope. In the development of this reform movement, the time press and printing press played an important role. Because the time press and the printing press played a big role in the growth of political and social consciousness of Turkestan population, and ideological unity against colonialism. Time press and printing made a revolution in the political and social life of Turkestan in a short period of time. Printing and periodical printing in the Turkestan region began after the conquest of the Russian Empire. The first printing house in Turkestan was established in 1868 in Tashkent under the headquarters of the military district. On April 28, 1870, the first newspaper "Turkestanskije vedomosti" began to be published, and in July, its Uzbek language

supplement "Gazette of the Turkestan Region" was published¹. This newspaper became an active propagandist of the colonial policy of the Russian Empire.

The Jadidist movement, which arose in Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century, paid great attention to the press together with Tatars in spreading its ideas of freedom and enlightenment. The Jadids cooperated with Tatars, Bashkirs, Azerbaijanis, Crimean Tatars, Russians and other nationalities in establishing newspapers and magazines in Turkestan. In this article, the activities of Tatar-Bashkir intellectuals in the establishment of time press and printing works in Turkestan are highlighted.

The contribution of Tatar and Bashkir enlighteners to the creation and development of modern press and printing works in Turkestan is very big. In 1870, the governor-general of Turkestan K.P. According to von Kaufman's order, the "Gazette of the Turkestan Region" was published as a supplement to the newspaper "Turkestanskije vedomosti". K.P. von Kaufman requested Muslim fonts from Petersburg to publish this newspaper. This newspaper was initially edited by Tatar printers Shohimardon Ibrohimov and M. Chanishev. Tatar typewriters Shahingirey Bekkulov, Abdulatif Yavushev, Ali Bektemirov worked². Although this newspaper promoted the colonial policy of the Russian Empire, it contributed to the development of the national press and printing industry.

The arrival of Tarjiman, Vaqt, Shura and similar newspapers published by Tatar and Bashkir intellectuals living in the central regions of the Russian Empire in Turkestan and spread among intellectuals increased the interest of Turkestan intellectuals in the time press. Because newspapers and magazines were the most convenient means for intellectuals to convey and spread their thoughts and ideas to the general public.

In June 1906, the first Uzbek national newspaper "Taraqqi" was published. This newspaper was edited by Ismail Abidi, a Tatar-Bashkir national. Abdulhamid Cholpon writes about this newspaper in his article entitled "Press in Turkistan" published in Baku: "Taraqqi" is a progressive newspaper, the editor of which is Ismail Abidi, a Tatar from the Russian interior. After the October Revolution, this person became a representative of the Left Socialist Revolutionary Party and served as the Commissar of Internal Affairs. After two months, it was approved by the government"³. Colonialism and bigotry were denounced in this newspaper. Articles calling on Muslims to wake up and educate the nation were published. He was banned because of his anti-government views.

In 1907, the newspaper "Shuhrat" was published by Abdulla Avloni, and in 1908, "Asiyo" was published by Ahmadjon Bektemirov. These newspapers were financially supported by the "Yosh Partiya" society founded by Tatar-Bashkir intellectuals in Kogan in 1906⁴. Akhmedjon Bektemirov belonged to the Tatar nationality and promoted the ideas of Turkism and Islamism in his newspaper. Because of this, the government put an end to its activities.

Ubaidulla Asadullohojayev was the editor-in-chief of the "Sadoi Turkistan" newspaper, which was published in April 1914, but the main articles were written by the Tatar journalist Abdurauf Muzaffarov. Another Tatar intellectual No'shiravon Yavushev participated in the activity of this newspaper with his articles⁵. Newspapers published articles calling for the reform of schools and madrasas, the expansion of new method schools, and the education of young people.

Tatar translator Osman Nuri worked in the newspaper "Sadoi Ferghana"⁶.

The famous Bashkir educator and figure Ahmad Zaki Walidiy made speeches in the Turkestan Time press with his articles filled with deep and free ideas.

The "Sho'roi Islam" newspaper, which was published in May 1917, was edited by the Tatar intellectual A. Battol, and another Tatar enlightener, No'shiravon Yavushev, was the editor⁷. On its pages, the newspaper promoted the ideas of developing relations between Turkestans and Turkic peoples living in other regions of Russia, reforming schools and madrasas.

From March 15, 1917, the newspaper "Fergana Page" was published under the editorship of Tatar printer Husayn Makayev⁸. Husayn Makayev was invited to Ferghana by Ishaq Khan Ibrat. This newspaper is distinguished by its fast and accurate delivery of news to its readers

In 1917, the newspaper "Ulug' Turkistan" was published by the Tatar bourgeoisie in Tashkent. After the February revolution, the Tatar bourgeoisie formed a society called "Union". This society decides to publish a newspaper in order to convey its thoughts and ideas. A. Battol from Tatarstan is invited to the editorship. After there was no response from him, the Tatar intellectual Kabir Bakir was appointed as the editor. "Nashriyot" company was formed with the participation of several rich and intellectuals in Tashkent, and Nadejda (Umid) printing house was bought from one person. "Ulug' Turkistan" newspaper is published in this publishing house⁹. This newspaper is a conservative newspaper, which promoted the ideas of developing national values, supporting autonomy, protecting private property, and uniting the people of Turkestan on the basis of a single cause and opinion.

On May 31, 1918, the newspaper "Khalq dorilfununi" began to be published in Tashkent. The editor was Mukhtar Bakir, the brother of the Tatar enlightener Kabir Bakir. Tatar intellectuals Abubakir Divayev and Fatih Bakir actively participated in this newspaper¹⁰. Since the newspaper was published after the October Revolution, it tried to stay away from politics as much as possible. The newspaper always repeated this on its pages. The goal of "Khalq dorilfununi" was to develop education, reform schools and madrasas, and free the people from ignorance.

After the October coup of 1917, the Bolsheviks, who took power in Turkestan, began to organize various press publications to spread their socialist ideas. The Bolsheviks used these newspapers to intensify the class struggle in Turkestan. Articles criticizing the holy religion of Islam were also published. A fight against Jadids was carried out. Articles discrediting the soldiers who fought for the independence of the country were published.

From September 1918, the newspaper "Ishchilar Kalkani" was published under the editorship of Tatar Tahir Fathullin as the official publication of the Soviet of Namangan workers-peasants and representatives of red soldiers¹¹. It was the most popular newspaper in Namangan.

On December 4, 1918, the newspaper "Khalq" began to be published in Kok. The responsible editor was Ahmad Devishev, a Tatar. Journalists of Tatar and Bashkir nationality - Ismail Berishev, Gani Tinchurin, Abdulla Aynullin, and others worked in the newspaper¹². The printed copy of the newspaper was between 1000-1500, some of which were paid and some of which were distributed free of charge. The newspaper stopped publishing in 39 issues.

From January 1921, the newspaper "Mehnat Bayrogi" was published as a disseminator of opinions of the Fergana regional factional committee. The responsible editor was the Tatar communist Kasim Sorokin, and later Ibrahim Rashidi. The slogan of the newspaper is "Long live the freedom of the East!", "Long live prosperity in the field of labor!" was¹³. "Labor Banner" was one of the sharpest publications in spreading the ideas of the Bolsheviks. He actively fought against the independence movement.

At that time, one of the biggest problems of the society was the lack of rights and education of Turkestan women. The enlightened women belonging to the Tatar-Bashkir nation showed great zeal in

covering the problems of the women of Turkestan in newspapers and magazines. For example, "Sadoi Turkistan" newspaper publishes an article by Tatar woman Sora Muzaffaria entitled "It's our fault". In this article, the author justifies the need to open jaded schools for women as well¹⁴. In "Samarkand" newspaper, Tatar woman Favziya Abdurashidova's sharp articles on girls' education are published¹⁵.

The articles of the Tatar enlightened woman Podsho Jalilova published in the newspaper "Sadoi Turkistan" are also of great importance¹⁶. In "Ulug' Turkistan" newspaper, the activities of women in the country were constantly covered under the column "Muslim Publishing Educational Society". Komila Burnasheva, an intellectual woman of Bashkir ethnicity, fights for women to have equal rights with men¹⁷. She speaks to newspapers with her articles on the issue of women's rights.

In conclusion, it can be said that the activity of Tatar-Bashkir enlighteners in the creation and development of modern press and printing works in Turkestan has not been deeply researched. This topic is waiting for its in-depth research. Newspapers published in Turkestan in cooperation with Tatar-Bashkir intellectuals introduced the subscribers to the events taking place in the world. The ideas of ridding the people of Turkestan of ignorance, reforming schools and madrasas, and enlightening the nation were put forward. Superstition and bigotry were fought against. In particular, articles condemning colonialism and supporting the freedom of Turkestan were published. Because of this, most of these newspapers were short-lived.

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